

Supplementary data of

Dysbiosis in PCOS: A Systematic Review of Microbiome Alterations Across Body Sites with GRADE Assessment of Evidence Quality

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Table S1: Quality assessments of the studies by Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS)

S.No	Study ID		Selection				Comparability		Exposure			Overall NOS Score
	First Author	Year of Publication	PCOS Diagnostic Criteria	Representativeness of the cases	Selection of Controls	Definition of controls	Cases and control with comparability of confounding factors such as BMI, Waist circumference, weight, and Height	Cases and control with comparable ages	Same methods used to assess microbiota in both cases and control	Validated method to measure microbiota (statistical analysis)	Evaluation of bacterial diversity	
1	Eyupoglu	2020	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	*	8
2	Liang	2020	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	8
3	Lindheim	2016	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	8
4	Dong	2021	*	*	*	-	*	-	*	*	*	7
5	Mammadova	2021	*	*	*	*	-	-	*	*	*	7

6	Li	2021	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	8
7	Lull	2021	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	9
8	Hassan	2022	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	8
9	Yin	2022	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	-	*	7
10	Chu	2020	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	7
11	Li	2024	*	*	*	-	-	*	*	*	*	7
12	Chen	2021	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	9
13	Li	2022	-	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	7
14	Liang	2021	*	*	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	8
15	Tu	2020	*	*	*	*	-	-	*	*	*	7
16	Jobira	2020	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	8
17	Hong	2020	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	9
18	Yang	2022	*	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	-	7
19	Wang	2022	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	9
20	Zhou	2020	*	*	*	-	-	*	*	*	*	7
21	Espinosa	2024	-	*	-	-	-	*	*	*	*	5
22	Zhou	2020	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	9
23	Chen	2024	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	*	8
24	Hong	2021	*	*	-	-	-	*	*	*	*	6
25	Jin	2023	*	*	*	-	-	*	*	*	*	7

26	Lu	2021	*	*	*	*	-	-	*	*	*	7
27	Zhang	2019	*	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	8
28	Lindheim	2017	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	*	8
29	Qi	2019	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	-	*	8
30	Yu	2022	*	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	*	8
31	Zhou	2023	*	*	*	-	-	*	*	*	*	7

Table S2: Summary of Qualitative Findings Table

Sr. No.	Summarized review findings	GRADE-CERQual assessment of confidence	Explanation of GRADE- CERQual assessment	References
1.	Slight changes in the microbiome of saliva.	Low confidence	No/Very minor concerns regarding methodological limitations, No/Very minor concerns regarding coherence, Serious concerns regarding adequacy, and No/Very minor concerns regarding relevance	Lindheim et al. 2016; Li et al. 2021;
2.	PCOS is associated with increased and decreased abundance of several taxa, at the phylum levels <i>Actinobacteria</i> , and <i>Proteobacteria</i> showed increase in abundance, whereas <i>Bacteroidetes</i> , and <i>Firmicutes</i> were less abundant. There was inconsistency at family, genus and species level in gut microbiome.	Low confidence	Serious concerns regarding methodological limitations, No/Very minor concerns regarding coherence, Moderate concerns regarding adequacy, and No/Very minor concerns regarding relevance	Dong et al. 2021; Chu et al. 2020; Li et al. 2024; Jobira et al. 2020; Yang et al. 2022; Chen et al. 2024; Eyupoglu et al. 2020; Liang et al. 2020; Mammadova et al. 2021; Lüll et al. 2021; Hassan et al. 2022; Yin et al. 2022; Li et al. 2022; Liang et al. 2021; Zhou et al. 2020; Zhou et al. 2020; Lindheim et al. 2017; Qi et al. 2019; Zhou et al. 2023; Yu et al. 2022; Chen et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2019;
3.	The abundance of genus <i>Lactobacillus</i> was reduced with slight increase in alpha diversity in the vagina.	Low confidence	No/Very minor concerns regarding methodological limitations, No/Very minor concerns regarding coherence, Moderate concerns regarding adequacy, and Serious concerns regarding relevance	Tu et al. 2020; Hong et al. 2020; Jin et al. 2023; Lu et al. 2021;
4.	Alpha diversity is reduced with	Moderate	No/Very minor concerns regarding methodological	Wang et al. 2022;

Hong, 2020	+	+	+	+	+	+	×	-
Yang, 2022	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	-
Wang, 2022	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Zhou, 2020	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Zhou, 2020	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
Chen, 2024	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-
Jin, 2023	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Lu, 2021	+	+	+	+	+	+	×	-
Zhang, 2019	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	×
Lindheim, 2017	+	+	-	+	+	+	×	-
Qi, 2019	+	+	+	+	+	-	×	-
Yu, 2022	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
Zhou, 2023	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-

+ indicates low risk of bias.

- indicates moderate risk of bias.

× indicates high risk of bias.

D1 - Bias due to Confounding - Studies that did not include confounding factors, such as BMI and age, showed a serious risk of bias.

D2- Bias in selection of participants into the study- Studies that recruited the patients from hospitals after diagnostic tests and control of healthy subjects (selection of case and control).

D3- Bias in classification of interventions- Rotterdam criteria are used for the diagnostic purpose of PCOS, and 16s rRNA gene sequencing is used to evaluate microbial profiles; if no, it indicates a high risk of bias.

D4- Bias due to deviations from intended interventions- Any deviations, such as suffering from other diseases than PCOS, can increase the risk of bias.

D5- Bias due to missing data- Data like study type, sample type, diversity assessment, tools, and bioinformatics pipelines were missing.

D6- Bias in measurement of outcomes- Proper bioinformatics tools and sequencing platforms were used to assess that the microbiota composition which can reduce the risk of bias.

D7-Bias in selection of the reported results- Reporting genera with significant p-values can increase the risk of bias.